

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE CLUSTER SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article is devoted to education at all times was considered an important component of the state's activity, an enduring value, because it is the basis of the economic development of society, one of the factors of social stability, a source of growth of the intellectual resource and the spiritual and moral potential of the population. At present, the educational needs of the population are growing, the number of applicants for higher, special, professional additional education is increasing.

Key words: innovative, approach, cluster, intellectual, education, effectively.

The cluster approach in education makes it possible to act effectively and successfully, bearing in mind the priority perspective common to all partners, it is advisable to coordinate joint educational activities. It is this type of activity that makes it possible to provide more effective assistance to members of the community who participate in the partnership, rationally approach its use, strive to remain different from each other, to recognize the differences of individuals and organizations.

In the context of the emerging innovative type of economy, domestic universities are faced with the acute problem of introducing innovations that can make universities more competitive and form a positive national competitiveness.

The modern education system has been in constant reform and renewal in recent years. At least, a lot of people talk and write about it.

The rapidity with which clusters and the policies associated with them have firmly entered the economic circulation has not given time for well-founded answers to questions about their essence and role in economic development. Clusters, depending on the context, mean many different structures, and the proposed mechanisms for supporting clustering processes are characterized by an extremely general nature and combine a wide range of traditional development policies. In practice, this often leads to non-obviousness and inefficiency of cluster policy measures, unpredictable, often opposite to the expected reaction of a complex object of regulation. Therefore, the formation of the cluster concept as a scientifically and practically proven approach should be preceded by an understanding of this concept and related phenomena. [2, 12-13].

It is generally accepted that clusters act as a means of increasing the competitiveness of territories, the transition to production processes with greater added value, and contribute to the establishment of constructive relationships between enterprises, research, educational, financial institutions and authorities. The cluster approach radically changes the content of regional and industrial policy, since the efforts of the authorities are directed to the development of a system of relationships between economic entities and state institutions. In practical terms, this approach is important primarily because it is environmental in nature.

The concept of "cluster" first gained its fame in economics in the 80s of the XX century, where it was first used in economic theory by Michael Porter. Here, a detailed description of the cluster formation mechanism was given as "a community of firms, closely related industries, mutually contributing to the growth of each other's competitiveness". M. Porter, as a popularizer of the definition of an economic cluster, showed that: "The competitiveness of a company is largely determined by the competitiveness of its economic environment, which, in turn, depends on the basic conditions (common resource) and competition within the cluster. [1]

What is an educational cluster? Let's start with a definition. A cluster is a combination of several homogeneous elements, which can be considered as an independent unit with certain properties [1]. A cluster is a group of neighboring interconnected companies and related organizations operating in a certain area, characterized by a common activity and complementary to each other [4]. A cluster is a group of geographically localized interconnected companies, suppliers of equipment, components, specialized services, infrastructure, research institutes, higher educational institutions and other organizations that complement each other and enhance the competitive advantages of individual companies and the cluster as a whole [8].

An educational cluster is a set of interconnected institutions of vocational education united by industry and partnerships with industry enterprises; it is a learning system mutual learning and self-learning tools in the innovation chain "science - technology business", based mainly on horizontal links within the chain [7].

The transitional (starting) model of the educational cluster is UNIK (educational and scientific innovation complex) [5]. The main goals of UNIK are: building an integral system of multi-level training of specialists for enterprises based on the integration of educational institutions and enterprises -employers, providing quality improvement, reduction of training time for specialists and retention of graduates in enterprises; intensification and stimulation of joint problem-oriented fundamental, exploratory and applied scientific research; creation of a flexible system for advanced training of specialists [9].

Cluster training is a relatively new direction in professional pedagogy, its introduction into the training process requires the definition of pedagogical conditions and experimental verification of the effectiveness of the formation of a competent specialist [3]. In other words, first you need to prepare a professional teacher who will train students - future specialists. The role of the university in the cluster is reduced to producing innovative goods. What does this mean in practice?

Research institutes and industrial establishments of the region become the base of practices and get the opportunity to participate in the formation of a specialist on their own scientific and educational base, in accordance with their needs and development prospects [10]. The cluster as a mechanism for innovative management of the development of the general education system makes it possible to ensure the effectiveness of the activities of each educational institution included in it, including: partnership, attraction of non-budgetary funds in the field of education, the emergence of resources for innovative training, retraining and advanced training of teaching staff, qualitatively new results of education based on the continuous development of the child, can improve the appearance of institutions [6].

Conclusion

Any state in the world strives to create an education system that allows students after graduation to be in demand both within their own country and abroad. Therefore, regarding the education system, the primary task of the state is to perform functions that are inaccessible to other participants in the educational process, such as financing, providing tax benefits and using other mechanisms to stimulate the educational services market, in order to train specialists qualified in the most promising areas of knowledge, through licensing and certification.

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